

Institute of
Materials Research
and Engineering

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

Damage detection using Direct-Write Piezoelectric Transducers and Lamb Waves in Composite Materials

Marilyne Philibert^{1,2}, Shuting Chen¹, Kui Yao¹, Constantinos Soutis^{3,4}, Matthieu Gresil^{2,4}

¹ Institute of Materials Research and Engineering, A*STAR (Agency for Science, Technology and Research), Singapore

² i-Composites Lab, School of Materials, University of Manchester, UK

³ Northwest Composite Centre, School of Materials, University of Manchester, UK

⁴ Aerospace Research Institute, University of Manchester, UK

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

CONFERENCE
DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

#ICCM22

Direct-Write Piezoelectric Transducers

Structural Health Monitoring

Application on aluminium plate [1]

- **P(VDF-TrFE)** sprayed
- Effective d_{33} of **-18 pm/V** (LSV at 1.5 kHz)
- Mode selection through electrode pattern

Rare applications on CFRP

- **BaTiO₃** particles [2] or **PZT** particles [3] in polymer matrix for passive sensing of impact

Objectives

- Apply *direct-write transducers* on CFRP plate using **P(VDF-TrFE)** coatings
- Develop **mode selection** through top electrode pattern design
- Use **active sensing** for damage detection

[1] Shen, Z., Chen, S., Zhang, L., Yao, K., & Tan, C. Y. (2017). Direct-Write Piezoelectric Ultrasonic Transducers for Non-Destructive Testing of Metal Plates. IEEE Sensors Journal, 17(11)

[2] J. F. Capsal, et al. "Piezoelectric sensing coating for real time impact detection and location on aircraft structures" (2012)

[3] K. Elkjaer, et al. "Integrated Sensor Arrays based on PiezoPaint for SHM Applications" (2013)

Fabrication and Mode selection

Fabrication

CFRP plates
250 x 225 x 2 mm

$$d_{33} = \frac{\text{displacement}}{\text{voltage}}$$

Effective d_{33} of -12 pm/V at 1.5 kHz
measured by Laser Scanning Vibrometer

Wavelength λ (mm)	Theoretical frequency A_0 mode (kHz)
2	676
4	325
6	208
8	148
10	112
12	88

$$\lambda = \frac{c_{\text{phase}}}{f}$$

Mode selection through top electrode pattern

Excitation: 5 tone burst sinusoidal + Hanning window, at 100 Vpp

Damage detection

AgNW: $\sim 0.08 \Omega/\text{mm}$
 P(VDF-TrFE): $\sim 34 \mu\text{m}$
 $\lambda = 12 \text{ mm}$

Path 1-3 \rightarrow no signal change
 Impact too small to be detected

Path 2-4 \rightarrow signal differences

Excitation: 5 tone burst sinusoidal + Hanning window, at 100 Vpp

Conclusion

- Direct-write piezoelectric transducers designed and fabricated on CFRP plate, by in-situ deposition, crystallization and patterning of **P(VDF-TrFE)** coatings
 - ✓ Good piezoelectric response: **effective d_{33} of - 12 pm/V** (LSV at **1.5 kHz**), but lower than for discrete PZT transducers (**low amplitudes**)
 - ✓ **Ability to select mode** through top electrode pattern
 - ✓ **Ability to detect impact damage** of 25 mm with electrode periodicity of 12 mm
- Further work:
 - Finite-elements modelling for understanding guided waves propagation through damage
 - Damage localisation method
 - Advantage of using direct-write transducers for damage detection compared to discrete transducers?
Mode selection?

Institute of
Materials Research
and Engineering

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

Thank you

Contact

Marilyne PHILIBERT

IMRE, A*STAR, Singapore
i-Composites Lab, The University of Manchester, UK

PhD Researcher

+65 9163 7262

marilyne.philibert@postgrad.manchester.ac.uk

Acknowledgments

A*STAR Research Attachment Programme (ARAP)

IMRE authors acknowledges partial support by SMI under the Asset Integrity & Risk Management (AIM) R&D Programme, Project ID: SMI-2015-OF-01, and Maritime Sustainability R&D Programme, Project ID: SMI-2015-MA-07

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

CONFERENCE
DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

#ICCM22